

Yield evaluation of F₁ hybrids in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam

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We evaluated 29 F₁ hybrids introduced from IRRI and 60 F₁ hybrids developed at CLRRI in yield trials with 3 replications 1983-86. Single seedlings were transplanted at 22 d, at 20- × 15-cm spacing in 2- × 2.5-m plots. Fertilizer was 40-30 kg PK/ha applied as basal and 75 kg N/ha in 3 equal splits: at puddling, tillering, and panicle initiation.

Nine percent of the combinations yielded significantly higher than check varieties NN3A and NN4B. The promising F₁ hybrids had 10-33% positive heterobeltiosis and 11-22% standard heterosis (see table). □

Yield, heterobeltiosis, and standard heterosis of some promising F₁ hybrids identified at CLRRI, Omon, Hau Giang, Vietnam, 1986.

Year	F ₁ hybrid	Yield (t/ha)	Heterobeltiosis (%)	Standard heterosis (%)
<i>Dry season</i>				
1983-84	V20A/NN4B	6.5	33.39	16.11
	97A/NN4B	5.5	17.57	10.50
	NN4B	4.8		
	CV (%)	15.3		
	LSD (0.05)	1.1		
1984-85	IR48483A/IR36	5.8	19.91	19.91
	IR48483A/IR54	5.5	10.00	14.10
	NN3A	4.8		
	CV (%)	16.7		
	LSD (0.05)	0.4		
1985-86	IR46831A/OM90	5.3	21.31	22.27
	NN7A	4.4		
	CV (%)	13.0		
	LSD (0.05)	0.5		
<i>Wet season</i>				
1985	V20A/NN3A	6.6	26.67	26.67
	NN3A	5.2		
	CV (%)	12.7		
	LSD (0.05)	0.6		
1986	IR46831A/OM90	6.2	17.73	17.78
	NN7A	5.2		
	CV (%)	13.6		
	LSD (0.05)	0.6		

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

TISSUE CULTURE

Induction of productive semidwarf mutants of Basmati rice

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Basmati rices are prized for their good cooking quality and aroma. Basmati 370, isolated from the local germplasm, currently is cultivated predominantly in Punjab Province. The cultivar is matchless in cooking quality and aroma, but is tall and has weak straw, so that it is unable to respond to fertilizer and to withstand lodging. Hybridization involving the Dee-Geo-Woo-Gen dwarfing gene source has been tried to modify these two inherent characters.

Induced mutation could be another approach. We induced semidwarf mutants of Basmati 370 during 1980.

Healthy uniform seeds of Basmati 370 with 14% moisture content were exposed to 0, 15, 20, and 25 kR from a

Performance of semidwarf mutants and parent Basmati 370 in micro yield trial.^a Faisalabad, Pakistan, 1983-84.

Mutant or variety	Plant height (cm)	Productive tillers (no./plant)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains (no./panicle)	Panicle fertility (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)
Basmati 370	177.0 a	9.3 b	30.6 a	112.3 a	85.3 a	21.3 a	3.6 b
SDM18 (15 kR)	132.8 b	10.9 a	28.0 c	121.6 a	89.1 a	19.1 b	4.5 a
SDM20 (15 kR)	133.2 b	11.8 a	28.3 c	119.5 a	88.9 a	19.3 b	5.1 a
SDM22 (15 kR)	134.1 b	11.3 a	29.2 b	127.3 a	89.1 a	19.3 b	5.2 a
SDM24 (20 kR)	132.8 b	11.8 a	29.2 b	127.4 a	89.6 a	19.3 b	5.4 a
SDM25 (20 kR)	131.5 b	11.3 a	28.3 c	124.3 a	89.5 a	19.1 b	5.2 a
SDM38 (25 kR)	131.8 b	12.0 a	28.4 c	118.0 a	89.3 a	19.5 b	5.2 a

^a In a column, figures followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance by DMRT.

⁶⁰Co source (5,000 seeds/ treatment). Seedlings were transplanted 1/hill at 15- × 15-cm spacing to suppress profuse tillering. Three first-emerging panicles per plant were harvested and bulked by treatment. The M₂ was grown at 1

seedling/ hill, 20- × 20-cm spacing.

Some semidwarf mutants were selected and their breeding behavior studied during 1982-83. True-breeding mutants (gross plant size 8 m²) were tested in a micro yield trial during 1983-

84, in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications. Seedlings were transplanted at 1/hill, 20- × 20 cm spacing. Fertilizer was 80-40-0 kg NPK/ha.

All mutant lines were 24-26% shorter than Basmati 370 (see table), but panicle

length and 1,000-grain weight were significantly inferior. Mutant strains were similar in grains per panicle and panicle fertility. Their yield potential was 25-51% higher than that of Basmati 370. The attribute of mutant lines that may enhance yield potential seems to be

higher number of productive tillers per plant.

All the mutants exhibited semidwarf plant posture along with higher yielding capability, and may be used directly and indirectly as new gene sources for short culm for Basmati rices. □

Pest Control and Management DISEASES

Effect of sclerotia size of *Rhizoctonia solani* on infectivity on rice plants

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Sclerotia of *R. solani*, the causal organism of rice sheath blight (ShB), are produced in large numbers on infected plants and often drop to the soil after harvest. Because they can survive for a long time, they tend to accumulate in the soil and are a primary source of inoculum. We examined sclerotia size and distribution in a naturally infested field and the effect of sclerotia size and number on infectivity of rice plants.

Surface soil from a ShB-infested ricefield was collected after harvest and processed in the laboratory. The sclerotia recovered were measured and grouped by size. The effect of sclerotia size and number on infectivity was tested by inoculating detached rice leaves and rice seedlings with different size and numbers of sclerotia recovered from soil or grown on potato dextrose agar (PDA). Sclerotia produced naturally, sizes 1 × 1, 1.5 × 1.5, 1.8 ×

Table 1. Effect of *R. solani* sclerotia size on infectivity on detached rice leaves.^a IRRRI, 1985.

Sclerotia size ^b (mm)	Lesions ^c (no.)	Lesion sized (mm)
2 × 2	5.1	19 × 5.6
1.8 × 1.8	4.3	17 × 4.5
1.5 × 1.5	2.8	13 × 4.1
1 × 1	1.2	9 × 4

^aData collected 4 d after inoculation. ^bSclerotia recovered from naturally infested soil. ^cNumber counted on each leaf blade inoculated: 2 replications with 10 blades each. ^dAv size lesion measured.

Table 2. Effect of *R. solani* sclerotia size and number on infectivity on rice plants^a in the greenhouse. IRRRI, 1985.

Number inoculated	Lesion length (mm)	Lesion number
<i>0.7 × 0.7 mm</i>		
1	0	0
2	0	0
3	0	0
4	9.5	2.9
5	10.4	5.2
<i>1 × 1 mm</i>		
1	10.5	4.3
2	11.4	5.1
3	14.0	8.2
4	15.2	11.8
5	16.5	13.6
<i>1.5 × 1.5 mm</i>		
1	17.8	12.4
2	19.2	14.9
3	20.2	16.3
4	20.6	17.0
5	20.7	17.4
<i>2 × 2 mm</i>		
1	20.6	10.3
2	21.1	14.5
3	22.0	22.5
4	22.2	28.4
5	23.7	31.6

^aRice cultivar IR36. Disease scoring 5 d after inoculation. Average tiller number/pot = 18.

1.8, and 2 × 2 mm, were inoculated at 1/leaf blade. Sclerotia produced on PDA, sizes 0.7 × 0.7, 1 × 1, 1.5 × 1.5, and 2 × 2 mm, were inoculated at 1 to 5/pot of seedlings. Lesions induced were counted and measured.

Sclerotia recovered from soil were 1 to 3 mm in size. The distribution frequency were 2.18% size 2 × 2 mm (or bigger), 12.18% 1.8 × 1.8 mm, 26.73% 1.5 × 1.5 mm, and 58.91% 1 × 1 mm.

Sclerotia size had a significant effect on infectivity. On detached rice leaves, average lesion number increased from

1.2 to 5.1 and average lesion size from 9 × 4 to 19 × 5.6 mm as sclerotia size increased from 1 × 1 to 2 × 2 mm (Table 1). On seedlings in pots, average lesion number increased from 0 to 31.6 and lesion length from 0 to 23.7 mm, as sclerotia size increased from 0.7 × 0.7 to 2 × 2 mm and sclerotia numbers from 1 to 5 (Table 2). □

Time of spraying to control sheath rot (ShR)

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We studied the effective time for fungicide application to control rice ShR in the greenhouse in two trials, five replications each.

The pathogen *Acrocyndrium oryzae* Sawada was multiplied in rice grain

Table 1. ShR development after fungicide sprays. TRRI, Aduthurai, India.

Treatment	ShR intensity at given days after treatment		
	5 d	10 d	15 d
Carbendazim 0.1%	0	3.7	6.3
Captafol 0.125%	0	0	6.3
Thiophanate methyl 0.1%	2.3	7.0	7.7
Carboxin 0.2%	3.7	6.3	7.7
Tridemorph 0.1%	3.0	7.0	7.7
Mancozeb 0.25%	2.3	7.0	8.3
Pyroquilon 0.1%	3.0	6.3	7.7
Iprodione 0.1%	3.7	6.3	7.7
Validamycin 0.1%	3.5	7.0	7.1
Kasugamycin 0.1%	3.7	6.3	7.0
Check	3.7	7.7	8.3
CD	1.2	1.5	ns ^a

^aNonsignificant.